

Taint Analysis as Configurable Program Analysis

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Abstract. Taint analysis is a technique that tracks the flow of sensitive information through a program. It can help identifying potential security vulnerabilities like data leaks or unauthorized access to sensitive data. We study the potential of using the Configurable Program Analysis (CPA) framework to implement static taint analysis. In this report, we first formulate the taint analysis problem as a CPA, called TaintAnalysisCPA. Then, we experiment using CEGAR and predicate abstraction with TaintAnalysisCPA to perform path-sensitive analysis. Furthermore, we explore the application of self-composition techniques to enhance the precision of taint analysis. Our approach aims to provide a sound and efficient solution for taint analysis within the CPA framework, offering an unified and extensible methodology for analyzing information flow properties in programs.

Keywords: Taint Analysis · CPA · Self-Composition.

1 Introduction

1.1 Taint Analysis

The goal of taint analysis is to identify how data from untrusted sources can influence the program's behavior, particularly in security contexts. A taint analysis usually consists of three main components:

- **Sources:** These are the points in the program where untrusted data enters, such as user inputs or external files.
- **Taint Propagation:** This is the process of tracking how tainted data flows through the program, affecting variables and operations.
- **Sinks:** These are the points in the program where tainted data can lead to security vulnerabilities, such as writing to a file or sending data over a network.

Implicit Flow Problem Sometimes, the flow of tainted data is not explicit in the program, but rather inferred through control flow. For example,

Listing 1. Implicit Flow Example

```
int x = tainted_input();
if (x > 0) {
    int y = 1;
```

```

} else {
    int y = 2;
}
// The value of y is implicitly
// influenced by the tainted input x.

```

Listing 2. Implicit Flow Example with Loop

```

int x = tainted_input ();
int y = 0;
for (int i = 0; i < x; i++) {
    y++;
}
// y = x

```

1.2 Configurable Program Analysis (CPA)

Configurable Program Analysis (CPA) is a framework that allows for the modular construction of program analyses. A CPA is defined as a 4-tuple

$$(D, \rightsquigarrow, merge, stop)$$

, where:

- D : The abstract domain, which defines the properties of the program states and the relationship between those states and concrete program states. The abstract states in an abstract domain form a semi-lattice $\epsilon = (E, \sqsubseteq, \sqcup, \top)$, where:
 - E : The set of all possible abstract states.
 - \sqsubseteq : A partial order relation that defines the order between two abstract states.
 - \sqcup : $a \sqcup b$ is the least upper bound of a and b , representing the combination of two abstract states.
 - \top : The top element of the semi-lattice, representing the most general abstract state.

- \rightsquigarrow :

$$\rightsquigarrow \subseteq E \times G \times E$$

is a transition relation that describes how the program state changes as the program executes.

- $merge$:

$$merge : E \times E \rightarrow E$$

is a merge function that tries to merge the first state into the second state.

- $stop$:

$$stop : E \times 2^E \rightarrow \{true, false\}$$

is a stop condition that determines when the analysis should terminate, such as reaching a fixed point or satisfying a certain property.

1.3 Motivation

There are little researches that use formal methods to perform static analysis of programs. We aim to explore the potential of using the CPA to perform sound static taint analysis.

1.4 Challenges

Challenges in static taint analysis include:

- Hard to strike the balance between soundness and precision.
- Tracking runtime properties is difficult.

2 Background and Related Work

2.1 Configurable Program Analysis (CPA)

Listing 3. CPAAlgorithm

```
def CPAAlgorithm(reached_states, waitlist, CPA):
    while waitlist:
        state = waitlist.pop()
        successors = CPA.leadsto(state)
        for next_state in successors:
            for reached in reached_states:
                merged = CPA.merge(next_state, reached)
                if merged != reached:
                    reached_states = reached_states - reached + merged
                    waitlist = waitlist - reached + merged

            if not CPA.stop(next_state, reached_states):
                reached_states.add(next_state)
                waitlist.add(next_state)
    return reached_states, waitlist
```

CPAChecker Dirk Beyer et al. introduced CPAChecker [1], the software checker that implements the CPA algorithm in Java.

TaintAnalysisCPA Diego Salgado implemented TaintAnalysisCPA [3] on gitlab. The taint analysis CPA is a 4-tuple

$$(D, \rightsquigarrow, merge, stop)$$

, consisting of:

- D : The abstract domain whose semi-lattice $\epsilon = (E, \sqsubseteq, \sqcup, \top)$ is defined as follows:

- E : The set of all possible taint states. A taint state is a tuple

$$(T, U, Predecessors)$$

- * T : map of tainted variables to expressions
- * U : map of untainted variables to expressions
- * $Predecessors$: set of predecessors of the state
- \sqsubseteq : Defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} a \sqsubseteq b &\iff b.T \text{ contains all info in } a.T \\ &\quad \wedge b.U \text{ contains all info in } a.U \\ &\quad \wedge a.Predecessors \subseteq b.Predecessors \end{aligned}$$

- \sqcup : $\forall s \in (T, U, Predecessors) : (a \sqcup b).s = a.s \cup b.s$
- \rightsquigarrow : The mapped expressions are updated according to the statement encountered. Variables could be moved to another map, depending on whether they are tainted or untainted by an assignment statement.
- $merge$: $MergeJoin(e1, e2) = e1 \sqcup e2$.
- $stop$: $StopSep(e, E) = \exists e' \in E . e \sqsubseteq e'$

2.2 CEGAR

CEGAR (Counterexample-Guided Abstraction Refinement) is a technique in program verification. The concept is to start with an abstract model of a program and check whether it satisfies a property. If the abstract model finds a counterexample, it is refined to eliminate the counterexample until a counterexample is concrete or no counterexample can be found.

Using CEGAR to refine predicates, CPAChecker can rule out infeasible paths.

2.3 Self-Composition

Weikun Yang et al. [2] introduced the lazy self-composition technique. It verifies whether the tainted sources influence the program’s behavior by checking whether the program behaves differently according to the tainted sources’ inputs.

3 Modifying TaintAnalysisCPA for path-Sensitive Analysis

3.1 Merge Operator

Problems with MergeJoin In order to perform path-sensitive analysis, we need to modify the TaintAnalysisCPA to support CEGAR and predicate abstraction. Using MergeJoin, TaintAnalysisCPA cannot specify the program path in which tainted values propagate.

Problems with MergeSeparate MergeSeparate always returns the second argument (the reached state) as the merged state. This causes infinite states in TaintAnalysisCPA since the successor will never be covered by the reached state, i.e. StopSep will never return true.

TaintMerge TaintMerge decides when to use mergeJoin or mergeSeparate based on whether the second state (reached state) "totally agrees" with the first state (successor).

"Totally agree" means that the tainted and untainted variables in the first state are a subset of the tainted and untainted variables in the second state. In this case, the join of the two states is returned.

Otherwise, it returns the second state.

3.2 Taint Analysis State

LessOrEqualOperator This Operator is changed to:

$$\begin{aligned} a \sqsubseteq b &\iff b.T.keySet \subseteq a.T.keySet \\ &\quad \wedge b.U.keySet \subseteq a.U.keySet \\ &\quad \wedge a.Predecessors \subseteq b.Predecessors \end{aligned}$$

Predecessors The Predecessors set in a TaintAnalysisState is now a set simplified TaintAnalysisState, status. Status contain only two sets of program variables, tainted and untainted.

3.3 Transfer Relation \rightsquigarrow

Two modifications are made to the transfer relation \rightsquigarrow in TaintAnalysisCPA:

- To reduce the number of states, we don't make a new state for an assume statement edge.
- After an failed property check, we mark the successor as error rather than the preceding state. In this way, CPAChecker will perform CEGAR correctly.

4 Experiment Results

4.1 Problem Sets

Diego Salgado sorted out and contributed a set of C programs. In this report, we fixed few of the programs to make them work as intended. Also, we provided a set of 14 C programs that are hard for TaintAnalysisCPA to analyse. We also provide a twin of this set of programs instrumented with `reach_error()` to test self-composition. We have a total of 194 C programs.

4.2 Experiment Setup

The experiment is performed on a VM machine with 17.6GB RAM and 6 cores. The host machine has 24 GB RAM and 8 AMD Ryzen 9 4900HS cores. The experiment is performed by benchexec with 120s time limit, 5GB memory limit, 2 CPU cores per task.

For self-composition experiments, we manually converted the programs from the C programs to self-composition form.

Listing 4. self-composition example

```

int main1 () {
    int x = nondet ();
    int a = foo(x);

    __VERIFIER_is_public(a, 1);
}

int main2 () {
    int x1 = nondet ();
    int a1 = foo(x1);

    int x2 = nondet ();
    int a2 = foo(x2);

    if (a1 != a2) {
        reach_error ();
    }
}

```

4.3 Unsupported Verification Goal

In the original design, TaintAnalysisCPA supports verifying the taintness of a variable at a program point. The verification goal can be specified by a `__VERIFIER_is_public(int var, bool flag)` function in the program.

However, since our TaintAnalysisCPA doesn't join states, verifying a variable must be taint will lead to a false alarm if there exists a path that the variable can indeed be untainted.

A list of test cases that contains this unsupported goal is given in appendix A.2.

Listing 5. False Alarm Example

```

int main () {
    int x = nondet ();
    if (x > 0) {
        x = 1;
    }
    // x could be tainted or untainted
}

```

```

// In the original design, the expected
// verdict for the checker is set to true.
__VERIFIER_is_public(x, 0);
return 0;
}

```

Nevertheless, we can still verify whether a variable is tainted at a program point by using only `__VERIFIER_is_public(var, 1)`. Our `TaintAnalysisCPA` is still sound and useful for taint analysis.

4.4 Results

Verification Correctness The verification results of `TaintAnalysisCPA` are shown in Table 1. Note that 12 of the wrong results in our modified `TaintAnalysisCPA` are caused by the unsupported verification goal mentioned above. 10 programs are unsolvable by both versions of `TaintAnalysisCPA`. They contain complex pointer arithmetic, unsupported C language features, or complex control flow that cannot be handled by `TaintAnalysisCPA`. Timeout occurs when SMT solver hangs or CEGAR falls into an infinite loop.

Table 1. Verification Results of `TaintAnalysisCPA`

		Original <code>TaintAnalysisCPA</code>			Modified <code>TaintAnalysisCPA</code>		
		numbers	walltime (s)	memory (MB)	numbers	walltime (s)	memory (MB)
All		194	1590	40500	194	1780	41500
Correct	All	180	1480	37500	170	1388	36000
	True	73	602	15200	64	520	13300
	False	107	876	22300	106	866	22700
Incorrect	All	14	114	2940	22	176	4740
	True	1	8.98	215	2	16.3	420
	False	13	105	2730	20 (incl. 12 unsupported)	159	4320
Timeout		0	–	–	2	215	734

Execution Time Fig 1 shows the quantile graph of the execution time of our modified `TaintAnalysisCPA` and the original `TaintAnalysisCPA`. The result showed that the modified `TaintAnalysisCPA` doesn't take much more time in most cases.

4.5 Self-Composition

The results of self-composition are shown in Table 2. It is worth noting that both versions of `TaintAnalysisCPA` correctly verified a program that self-composition failed to verify.

Fig. 1. quantile graph of the original and the modified TaintAnalysisCPA. Y-axis is the logged execution time.

5 Discussion and Future Work

5.1 Weakness of Current Approaches

Currently, no approaches can handle recursive functions. We have to config CPAChecker to skip recursive functions. This causes our analysis to be unsound. A recursive program in our test set A.1 is shown in the appendix. TaintAnalysisCPA cannot correctly analyse pointer arithmetic in C programs.

5.2 Conclusion

TaintAnalysisCPA is an efficient static taint analysis algorithm, while self-composition technique is useful for verifying programs with implicit flow taintness.

5.3 Future Work

Inspecting the when CEGAR will fall into an infinite loop can help us to improve the performance of TaintAnalysisCPA. Secondly, the usage of TaintAnalysisCPA with other algorithms, such as Interpolation-based Model Checking, could be explored. Finally, we can explore the potential of using other abstract domains, such as ValueCPA, to "strengthen" the taint analysis states.

References

1. Daniel Baier, Dirk Beyer, Po-Chun Chien, Marie-Christine Jakobs, Marek Jankola, Matthias Kettl, Nian-Ze Lee, Thomas Lemberger, Marian Lingsch-Rosenfeld, Henrik Wachowitz, and Philipp Wendler: Software Verification with CPAChecker 3.0: Tutorial and User Guide (Extended Version) <https://arxiv.org/abs/2409.02094>
2. Weikun Yang, Yakir Vizel, Pramod Subramanyan, Aarti Gupta, and Sharad Malik: Lazy Self-Composition for Taint Analysis https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-96142-2_11

3. Diego Salgado: Branch Taint_Analysis_CPA of CPAChecker on Gitlab https://gitlab.com/sosy-lab/software/cpachecker/-/tree/Taint_Analysis_CPAChecker?ref_type=heads

A Appendix

A.1 Recursive Program Example

Listing 6. Recursive Program Example

```
int main() {
    int y = foo(20);

    __VERIFIER_is_public(y, 0);
}

int foo(int n) {
    int r;
    int tainted = __VERIFIER_nondet_int();

    if (n > 1)
        r = n * foo(n - 1);
    else
        r = tainted;

    return r;
}
```

A.2 List of unsupported test cases

- c_infix_operators/ternaryOperatorSafe_bothBranchesReachable.c
- extern_benchmarks/innerIfSafe_1.c
- extern_benchmarks/readMetricsBasicRecursionSafe_1.c
- extern_benchmarks/readMetricsBasicRecursionSafe_2.c
- extern_benchmarks/simpleCondForLoopSafe.c
- extern_benchmarks/simpleIfSafe_3.c
- extern_benchmarks/simpleIfSafe_4.c
- extern_benchmarks/simpleInterProcPrintResultsSafe.c
- extern_benchmarks/simpleWhileLoopSafe_4.c
- extern_benchmarks/simplePrepareSliceSafe_2.c
- allLoopsSafe_2.c
- conditionalDataflowSafe_2.c

	Self-Comp			Original TaintAnalysisCPA			Modified TaintAnalysisCPA		
	numbers	walltime (s)	memory (MB)	numbers	walltime (s)	memory (MB)	numbers	walltime (s)	memory (MB)
All	14	315	3260	14	115	2950	14	228	3110
Correct	11	2220	All	5	42.6	1060	8	80.6	1730
	True	38.6	1090	3	24.4	637	6	48.1	1270
False	6	58.5	1350	2	18.2	428	2	32.5	463
All	1	8.32	225	9	72.1	1880	5	39.7	1070
Incorrect	True	-	-	0	-	-	0	-	-
False	0	-	-	9	-	-	5	-	-
Timeout	3	174	821	0	-	-	1	108	311

Table 2. Verification Results of Self-Composition